

APPLIED CORPORATE FINANCE

COMPANY: KINDER MORGAN INC.

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1. Corporate Governance Analysis

Richard D. Kinder and William V. Morgan used an innovative MLP fundraising mechanism as a development vehicle to create a utility firm in 1997. Among the biggest energy infrastructure businesses in North America at the moment is KMI. The corporation employs over 11,000 people in North America and owns or manages 140 refineries and about 82,000 miles of infrastructure. The CEO and Executive Director who is still working as a member of the board of directors is Richard D. Kinder's net worth is 8.1 billion dollars according to Forbes 2023.

Our total number of corporate boards is 13, including CEO Kinderman:

- The CEO is the highest-ranking executive in the company, oversees day-to-day operations and is primarily responsible for making strategic decisions and setting the overall direction of the organization, with all major responsibilities focused on him.
- The chair of the board of directors typically presides over board meetings, ensures proper governance practices are followed, and represents the board to external stakeholders.
- The role of the chair of the board of directors is to provide leadership to the board, ensure effective communication among board members, oversee strategic planning and decision-making processes, and act as a liaison between the board and senior management.

Our company has a CEO duality as the CEO Executive Chairman Kinderman also serves as the chair of the board of directors. This means the same individual holds the CEO and board chair roles within the organization. The Executive director who has been selected via the vote of the board of directors in 2023 is Kimberly A. Dong.

According to the organization's registration of formation, the bylaws will determine the number of directors, if any. According to the rules and regulations, a majority of the Board must periodically decide how many governors to have. Every year, the executive committee will assess the current composition of directors and adjust the number of individuals as necessary.

The board is aware that problems of independence of non-executive directors may arise if the salaries and other fees and benefits of the board members exceed what is usual. The Board is also aware that similar concerns about the independence of non-executive directors may arise when the Company makes significant charitable donations to organizations with which the non-executive director is affiliated or enters into consulting agreements (or otherwise gives indirectly). compensation to directors. The Board intends to evaluate these issues when deciding the size and amount of the remuneration of the Board KMI always provides the board of directors yearly salary in “PCAOB”.

NAME AND TITLE	TOTAL COMPENSATION	PAY RANK BY TITLE In Energy & Utilities Industry
Steven J. Kean Chief Executive Officer	\$1 View details	#341 View more
Kimberly A. Dang President	\$6,888,338 View details	#5 View more
Dax A. Sanders Vice President (President, Products Pipelines)	\$3,051,329 View details	#2 View more
David P. Michels Vice President and Chief Financial Officer	\$2,738,342 View details	#107 View more
James E. Holland Vice President and Chief Operating Officer	\$3,078,329 View details	#40 View more

(Board of Directors in Kinder Morgan Inc, Salary.com, 2022)

Without consideration of racial or ethnic background shade, creed, sex, pregnancies, deliveries, and related illnesses, sex (including gender identity and expression), sexual orientation, national origin, ancestry, or citizenship, age, mental or physical disability, genetic information, married status, the armed forces or veteran status, family status, status as an individual authorized to work in the United States, or any other circumstance granted protection by law, Kinder Morgan offers equal employment possibilities to all of its staff members and potential applicants (Wall Street Journal, 2023). The sole female member of the board of directors and the chief executive officer is Ms. Kimberly Dong.

- **ESG Policies:**

Strategy for the environment: Invest in an environmentally friendly future invest in CCUS and alternative fuel downstream assets. Expand natural gas transmission/storage, RSG, RNG, and LNG companies. Evaluate hybridization potential. Energy Transition Ventures Group's primary focus is exploring our

larger opportunities. Work: We minimize greenhouse gases, lessen the influence of our operations on our surroundings, and lessen the impact on biological variety.

- ***Social Policies:***

We expect employees and contractors to follow our business and ethical rules and supplier guidelines. Promote a safety-focused culture We build and maintain relationships with stakeholders where we operate. Promote a diverse, inclusive, and respectful workplace to support employee careers.

- ***Governance Policies:***

Board of directors committees including audit, reimbursement EHS, and suggesting and administration use the operations governance framework for regular risk management tasks. Potential risks and possibilities are tracked and reported to the senior management board for assessment of long-term business strategy for sustainability and adaptation mechanisms.

Kinder Morgan, Inc. (NYSE: KMI) today announced the release of its 2022 Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Report. The report highlights a reduction of approximately 2.6 percent in Scope 1 emissions from KMI's operations and continued reductions in methane emissions that affect total Scope 1 emission. It also shows KIM's efforts to reduce methane intensity by expanding annual leak detection surveys to cover 100% of natural gas gathering and booster compressor stations. Also, the company's investment in two renewable diesel hubs in California, a renewable raw material storage and logistics center in Harvey, Louisiana, and its growing renewable natural gas platform. The 2022 report also includes new or expanded disclosures that assess the company's carbon reductions for major greenhouse gas sources, climate advocacy and union alignment, and metrics related to the percentage of female or minority employees. `We are very pleased. to announce. Scope 1 emissions are decreasing year-on-year, particularly after new projects have been introduced over the past year," said James Holland, former CEO of KMI. "We will continue to support the energy transition by increasing our commitment to renewable fuels and investing in other low-carbon projects that deliver shareholder value.". KPI always discloses its ESG policy in annual PPT formation.

2. Working Capital Management

As of June 30, 2018, and December 31, 2017, correspondingly, Kinder Morgan Inc. had working capital deficits of \$2,745 million and \$3,466 million, which are measured as current assets and fewer current liabilities. Short-term loans used to fund the company's capital expenditures for enlargement may be included in its current liabilities; normally, they anticipate repaying these loans with retained earnings from activities. The net reduction in accrued interest and the higher amount of maturing debt that was refinanced with long-term debt in the first half of 2018 were the main causes of the \$721 million (21%) improvement from year-end 2017. The timing of established repayments of debt, variations in the collection and exchange of receivables and accounts payable, changes in the actual worth of our derivative obligations, and variations in our cash and cash equivalent balances as a result of excess cash from operations after payments for financing and investing are some of the factors that generally cause our working capital complement to fluctuate.

An increase in cash related to gas in underground gas storage inventory, which came about as a result of lower storage administered along with price declines when compared to the 2017 period, as well as higher payments for litigation matters in 2017, contributed to the \$215 million increase associated with net changes in working capital items and non-current assets and liabilities. Additionally, the \$416 million decline in net income resulting from the period-to-period net increase in non-cash items included the following factors. liabilities from disposals and limitations, net, and equity investment.

(Kinder Morgan Inc. Ratios, Investing.com, 2023)

Between the fiscal years concluding in December 2019 and December 2023, Kinder Morgan's return on invested capital ran at a median return of 4.8%, with an average return of 4.7%. In addition to decreasing in 2020 (4.0%, -6.1%) and 2022 (4.8%, -9.1%), Kinder Morgan's return on investment for invested capital climbed in 2019 (4.2%, +1.7%), 2021 (5.3%, +34.0%), and 2023 (5.1%, +6.3%). In December 2020, the company's return on invested capital reached a 5-year lowest of 4.0%. This is critical when contrasting ROI evaluations to the standards of the sector or the company's cost of capital. In the context of the event that the cost of capital surpasses 5.1%, it might suggest that Kinder Morgan's profits are insufficient to offset its expenses. As an example, Williams, one of Kinder Morgan's primary competitors had a 7.4% ROI over this period.

This is the value that the company will use to make sales and cover its short-term expenses. Working capital is a measure of a company's short-term financial health as well as its efficiency. Industry-specific working capital requirements varied. A current ratio of 1.5 to 3 (current assets to current liabilities) is traditionally regarded as a good liquidity situation. But it's important to keep in mind that the best working capital can only be determined concerning certain conditions.

Over the past 10 years, Kinder Morgan, Inc.'s typical historical current ratio has been 0.57. Comparing the current 0.35 Current Ratio to the historical average, 6.03% has changed. KMI's current ratio peaked

in the September 2018 quarter at 1.05, the highest level during the previous 10 years (40 quarters). The September 2019 quarter saw the Current Ratio reach its lowest point, at 0.35. Whenever Kinder Morgan's current ratio is less than 1, it suggests that it could find it difficult to satisfy its short-term financial commitments using its current assets alone and that it might find it difficult to make its debt payments on time. It implies that the business can be significantly dependent on short-term loans or additional funding to pay its debts.

The working capital policy determines a firm's current assets and liabilities. There are three different working capital policies: aggressive, moderate, and conservative. Each of these measures includes a risk-reward trade-off. A firm may take an aggressive strategy by holding a small proportion of its assets in current assets or using a substantial amount of short-term debt. The implementation of this strategy will increase profitability and risk for the firm. The executive team of a company must weigh the anticipated return against the potential hazards to determine the working capital management policy. The state of optimal working capital arises from striking an equilibrium between effectiveness and volatility. According to the balance statement of Kinder Morgan Inc., total current liabilities were \$7.221 billion in 2023 and total current assets were \$2.542 billion. We will have a negative working capital if we use the provided data to compute working capital (total current assets - total current liabilities). This leads us to the conclusion that Kinder Morgan Inc. has an aggressive working capital policy. Reducing working capital for Kinder Morgan Inc. may make it more difficult for the energy business to compensate providers on time or fulfil operating costs when there is an unexpected fluctuation in the flow of funds that amounts to \$4,049 billion.

3. Measuring Investment Returns

The \$1.82 billion deal that Kinder Morgan is anticipated to execute in the first quarter of 2024 to acquire NextEra Energy Partners LP's oil and gas pipeline infrastructure in South Texas was not included in the projection. The Eagle Ford basin is connected to Mexico and the Gulf Coast by the pipeline owned by South Texas Midstream LLC (STX Midstream). It is connected to the Kinder Morgan pipelines as well (Kinder Morgan Inc., 2023). When factoring a full-year EBITDA contribution from the asset, Kinder Morgan Inc. had originally intended to fund the deal using cash on hand and short-term borrowings, raising our net debt-to-EBITDA ratio by around 0.1 numerous times.

The acquisition comes after Kinder Morgan's second Eagle Ford pipeline, which is linked to a pipeline that STX Midstream owns 50% of, goes into operation. Its acquisition in consideration wouldn't harm Kinder Morgan's finances. As of the conclusion of the third quarter, it reported having around \$3.6 billion in borrowing capacity and \$80 million in cash and cash equivalents. In a quarterly governmental filing on October 18, it stated, "We have consistently generated substantial cash flows from operations, providing a source of funds of \$4,169 million and \$3,563 million in the first nine months of 2023 and 2022, consecutively." (Jov Onsat, 2023) Based on its anticipated financial results and including commercial collaborations, KMI expects the investment to be accretive to its stockholders. The purchase price represents an 8.6-fold multiple of EBITDA in 2024 and a 7.0-7.5-fold long-term investment-to-EBITDA several. This information was stated in the acquisition disclosure.

4. Stockholders Analysis and Capital Structure Choice

Based on recent financial reports and Kinder Morgan's current share price, the company's outstanding shares will range from 2,220,000,000 to 2,270,000,000 between 2018 and 2022. At the end of 2022, there will be 2,250,000,000 shares outstanding. Kinder Morgan's market capitalization at the end of 2022 was \$40.64 billion, with an enterprise value of \$71.90 billion.

The ownership structure of Kinder Morgan (KMI) shares is a mix of institutional, retail, and individual investors. Institutional investors, totalling more than 1.3 billion shares, owned about 62% of the company. Insiders own 16% of the shares, approximately 360 million shares, and 22% was held by public companies and individual investors, totalling more than 470 million shares. Richard Kinder is the largest shareholder with 12% of the outstanding shares. Other major institutional shareholders include Vanguard Group Inc (7.78%), BlackRock Inc (6.89%), and State Street Corp (5.72%).

In 2022, Kinder Morgan, Inc. (KMI) used the following types of financing to raise funds: dividends, share repurchases, net income, cash flow, and debt financing. The company paid a dividend of \$1.11 per share. Share repurchases were \$750 million. Net income for the year was \$2.5 billion and distributable cash flow (DCF) per share was \$2.07.

From 2018 to 2022, Kinder Morgan Inc.'s weighted average cost of capital (WACC) will gradually change, both upwards and downwards. Initial data for 2018 showed a WACC of 4.64%, reflecting low long-term financing rates and a moderate cost of equity.

However, over time, from 2019 to 2022, the company's WACC gradually changed. It increased to 5.59% in 2019, decreased to 4.36% in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and continued to fluctuate to 6.06% and 7.02% in 2021 and 2022, respectively. These changes reflect the impact of financial and market factors on the company, including changes in the cost of capital and investor demand for expected returns with increased risk.

Kinder Morgan Inc.'s debt-to-capital ratio is gradually decreasing over the period from 2018 to 2022. For example, in 2018, the ratio was 107.2%, with debt of US\$38 billion compared to equity of US\$35 billion. In 2019, this ratio decreased to 102%, with debt of \$35,880 billion and equity of \$35,161 billion. In 2020, equity fell to \$34,889 billion and debt to \$34,391 billion, bringing the debt-to-equity ratio down to 98.6%. The same ratio maintained in 2021. However, in 2022, debt also falls to USD 32,193 billion, while equity is USD 32,114 billion, resulting in a debt-to-equity ratio of 100.2%. Over the last 5 years, this ratio has decreased by 7%, indicating that the company is reducing its reliance on debt relative to equity. This trend can be seen as a positive signal to investors and other stakeholders.

Based on the above information about Kinder Morgan's debt and equity from 2018 to 2022, we can see that the company has been consistently reducing its debt ratio, which may indicate that the company is looking to reduce its reliance on debt and improve its financial strength. Noting that Kinder Morgan operates in an industry with relatively stable and predictable earnings, we can set the recommended gearing ratio between 30% and 50%. This range allows the company to provide sufficient financial stability while maintaining some flexibility to fund future investment projects and strategic objectives.

5. Dividend Policy

- ***Dividend Policy Recommendation***

Given the current scenario, I recommend that Kinder Morgan Inc. adopt a stable dividend policy. A stable dividend policy provides consistency to shareholders, indicating a commitment to sharing profits while also allowing the company to retain sufficient funds for growth and operational needs. This policy aligns with Kinder Morgan's position in the energy infrastructure sector, which typically generates stable cash flows.

- **Changes in Dividend Payout Ratio**

(Dividend Payout Ratio of Kinder Morgan Inc., Gurufocus.com,2024)

There has been a slight increase in Kinder Morgan's dividend payout ratio over the past few years. Kinder Morgan's dividend payout ratio for the months ended in Dec. 2023 was 1.05. Currently, it is 1.06, which seems too high. During the past 13 years, the highest Dividend Payout Ratio was 38.46. The lowest was 0.78. And the median was 1.25. As of today, the Dividend Yield % is 6.44%. During the past 13 years, the highest Trailing Annual Dividend Yield was 14.85%. The lowest was 2.18%. And the median was 4.77%. Dividends per Share for the months ended in Dec. 2023 were \$0.28. This increase can be attributed to several factors, including the company's improved financial performance, increased cash flows from operations, and management's desire to reward shareholders. Additionally, as Kinder Morgan completes major projects and reduces capital expenditures, more funds become available for distribution to shareholders in the form of dividends.

- **Price-Earnings Ratio Trends**

(PE Ratio of Kinder Morgan Inc., Gurufocus.com,2024)

The price-earnings (P/E) ratio of Kinder Morgan has experienced fluctuations over the last five years. As of today, the company's share price is \$17.56. Earnings per Share (Diluted) for the trailing twelve

months (TTM) ended in Dec. 2023 were \$1.07. Therefore, the P/E Ratio for today is 16.41. During the past 13 years, the highest PE Ratio of Kinder Morgan was 1952.00. The lowest was 12.86. And the median was 31.43. This reflects investors' perception of the company's future earnings potential and risk. Increases in the P/E ratio could indicate growing investor confidence, improved earnings prospects, or favorable market conditions. Conversely, decreases may signal concerns about the company's growth prospects, industry challenges, or economic conditions.

- ***Potential Changes in Dividend Policy***

Considering the current cash balance and financial performance of Kinder Morgan, there may not be an immediate need to change the dividend policy drastically. However, periodic evaluations should be conducted to ensure that the policy remains aligned with the company's financial objectives, investment opportunities, and shareholder preferences. If significant growth opportunities emerge or if the company faces financial constraints, adjustments to the dividend policy may be warranted.

- ***Strategies to Enhance Firm Value***

To enhance value at Kinder Morgan, I could pursue several strategic initiatives:

1. **Optimize Capital Allocation:** Continuously evaluate investment opportunities and allocate capital to projects with the highest potential returns. This includes expanding existing infrastructure assets, pursuing strategic acquisitions, and diversifying revenue streams.
2. **Cost Efficiency Measures:** Implement cost-saving initiatives to improve operational efficiency and margins. This could involve streamlining processes, leveraging technology, renegotiating contracts, and optimizing resource allocation.
3. **Debt Management:** Manage debt levels prudently to maintain financial flexibility and lower borrowing costs. Refinancing debt at favourable terms and reducing interest expenses can enhance profitability and shareholder value.
4. **Sustainable Growth:** Prioritize sustainable practices and invest in renewable energy projects to capitalize on emerging trends and meet evolving regulatory requirements. This not only aligns with environmental and social responsibilities but also enhances long-term profitability and competitiveness.

- 5. Enhance Stakeholder Communication:** Maintain transparent communication with investors, analysts, and other stakeholders to build trust and confidence in the company's strategic direction and performance. This includes providing timely updates on financial results, operational developments, and corporate governance practices.

In conclusion, adopting a stable dividend policy, optimizing capital allocation, managing costs effectively, and pursuing sustainable growth initiatives are essential for enhancing value at Kinder Morgan Inc. By implementing these strategies, the company can achieve sustainable growth, maximize shareholder returns, and maintain its position as a leading player in the energy infrastructure sector. Periodic reviews and adjustments to the dividend policy should be undertaken to ensure alignment with the company's evolving needs and market conditions.

6. References

- Salary.com (2022). Board of Directors in KINDER MORGAN INC. [online] Salary.com. Available at: <https://www1.salary.com/kinder-morgan-inc-Executive-Salaries.html>.
- Wall Street Journal (2023). Kinder Morgan Holdco LLC. [online] WSJ. Available at: <https://www.wsj.com/market-data/quotes/KMI/company-people>.
- Kinder Morgan Inc. (2023). *Kinder Morgan Announces 2024 Financial Expectations*. [online] Kinder Morgan. Available at: <https://ir.kindermorgan.com/news/news-details/2023/Kinder-Morgan-Announces-2024-Financial-Expectations/default.aspx>.
- Jov Onsat (2023). *Kinder Morgan Expects to Spend \$2.3B in Capex for 2024*. [online] Rigzone. Available at: https://www.rigzone.com/news/kinder_morgan_expects_to_spend_23b_in_capex_for_2024-06-dec-2023-174961-article/.
- Jon Chesto (2023). *Kinder Morgan shelves \$3 billion pipeline project*. [online] The Construction Association. Available at: <https://www.agcnys.org/articles/kinder-morgan-shelves-3-billion-pipeline-project/>.
- Wisesheets (2023). *Kinder Morgan, Inc. (KMI) Historical Current Ratio*. [online] Available at: <https://www.wisesheets.io/current-ratio/KMI>.
- Investing.com (2023). *Kinder Morgan Inc. Ratios*. [online] Investing.com. Available at: <https://www.investing.com/equities/kinder-morgan-ratios>.
- Macrotrends (2023). *Kinder Morgan Return on Investment 2010-2023*. [online] macro trends. Available at: <https://www.macrotrends.net/stocks/charts/KMI/kinder-morgan/roi>.
- Alpha Spread (2023). *KMI's Weighted Average Cost of Capital (WACC)*. [online] AlphaSpread. Available at: <https://www.alphaspread.com/security/nyse/kmi/discount-rate>.
- Simply Wall Street (2023). *Kinder Morgan Balance Sheet Health*. [online] Simply Wall St. Available at: <https://simplywall.st/stocks/us/energy/nyse-kmi/kinder-morgan/health>.

- Wall Streetzen (2024). Kinder Morgan Inc Stock Ownership - Who owns Kinder Morgan? [online] WSZ. Available at: <https://www.wallstreetzen.com/stocks/us/nyse/kmi/ownership>.
- Stock Analysis (2024). Kinder Morgan, Inc. (KMI). [online] Stock Analysis. Available at: <https://stockanalysis.com/stocks/kmi/>.
- Yahoo Finance. (n.d.). *Kinder Morgan, Inc. (KMI) Valuation Measures & Financial Statistics*. [online] Available at: <https://finance.yahoo.com/quote/KMI/key-statistics>.
- Kinder Morgan Inc. (n.d.). *Kinder Morgan - Investor Relations*. [online] Available at: <https://ir.kindermorgan.com/home/default.aspx>.
- Safina, J. (n.d.). *Council Post: How to Increase Your Company's Value*. [online] Forbes. Available at: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesfinancecouncil/2021/03/05/how-to-increase-your-companys-value/?sh=23f14807340a>.
- Gurufocus.com (n.d.). *KMI (Kinder Morgan) Dividend Payout Ratio*. [online] Available at: <https://www.gurufocus.com/term/payout/KMI/Dividend-Payout-Ratio/KMI>.
- Gurufocus.com (n.d.). *KMI (Kinder Morgan) PE Ratio*. [online] Available at: <https://www.gurufocus.com/term/pettm/KMI/PE-Ratio/KMI>.
- Yahoo Finance. (2024). *Kinder Morgan Inc's Dividend Analysis*. [online] Available at: <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/kinder-morgan-incs-dividend-analysis-100425821.html>.